

Mediating Effect of Debugging Strategies on the Relationship Between Language Learning Strategies and English Proficiency of the Students

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Abstract. The current study aimed to evaluate whether debugging strategies mediate the relationship between Language Learning Strategy and English Proficiency of the students. In this study, the researcher selected 200 junior high school students in Cluster 5 Schools in Davao City Division as the study's respondents. A stratified random sampling technique was utilized in the selection of the respondents. A non-experimental quantitative research design using a descriptive-correlational method was employed. The data collected were subjected to the following statistical tools: Mean, Pearson Moment Product Correlation, and Structural equation model using mediation analysis. Findings revealed that the students' debugging strategies, language learning strategies, and English proficiency were described as extensive. Further, correlation analysis demonstrated a significant relationship among the students' debugging strategies, language learning strategies, and English proficiency. Evidently, SEM using mediation analysis proved that debugging strategies mediate the relationship between language learning strategies and English proficiency of the students in Cluster 5 Schools in Davao City. In other words, debugging strategies significantly mediate the relationship between language learning strategies and the students' English proficiency in Cluster 5 Schools in Davao City. Lastly, it was found that debugging strategies mediate the relationship between language learning strategies and English proficiency of the students in Cluster 5 Schools in Davao City.

KEY WORDS

1. teaching English.
2. debugging strategies.
3. language learning strategies.
4. English proficiency

Date Received: October 05, 2024 — Date Reviewed: November 10, 2024 — Date Published: December 10, 2024

1. Introduction

Effective teaching strategies bring positive learning outcomes to the students. They allow teachers to think critically and rationally about their practices inside and outside the classrooms. They help generate students' interest and promote deep and long-lasting learning. Effective teaching strategies are vital to creating an engaging classroom environment that encourages student learning. Different strategies can help engage students in the class and allow them to explore topics on their own terms. Moreover, to give some more flavor into the impact of the relationship between language learning strategies and the student's English proficiency by mediat-

ing or involving another variable, the debugging strategies as a mediating variable. In the United States, Benaou (2016) highlighted that the low passing rates of students in high school English language proficiency tests remain an increasing problem among secondary educators worldwide. The report of Clotfelter in 2015 showed that the low proficiency level in the English language resulted in gaps in conceptual understanding of students' language skills, thus decreasing students' feelings of adequacy and enjoyment. According to Russakoff, in 2011, almost 10 percent of the population of non-English native students from ages 12-17 years showed a low level of English proficiency that led to difficulties in interacting and socializing with native English speakers. On the other hand, Schraw and Dennison (1994) defined debugging strategies as the individual's skills and strategies used to correct comprehension and performance errors. According to Kalmari (2017), using motivational strategies has been more critical than learning motivation because learner-motivating skills should be considered central to teaching effectiveness. Likewise, Cicekc and Sadik (2019) asserted that attention is the first step in the learning process. Through this, students can focus on the meaning and significance of new information. Taking things in the Philippine setting, Cabigon 2015 found that the low proficiency levels in the English language among students resulted in a growing number of unfilled jobs in various industries that require certain levels of English communication skills. Raffy-Tima (2018) mentioned that low proficiency levels in the English language among students are due to the reason that teachers have been using Filipino as a medium of instruction even in Math and Science subjects. Moreover, Racca and Lasaten (2016) reported that passers-by for board examinations of the Professional Regulatory Commission in all fields of endeavor continue to go down, which is attributed to their low proficiency in the English language. Relative to the said claim, it was pointed out that students' proficiency in other subjects, such as Science and Mathematics, was affected by the student's level of proficiency in the English language. The report further showed that their skills in problem-solving were only 53 percent, analysis was 56 percent; and computation was 62 percent. These skills all require proficiency in English. On the contrary, Rafiu and Nwalo (2016) argue that students who are highly proficient in the English language exhibit the ability to speak or perform in an acquired language. More so, Mojabi (2014) illustrated that highly proficient students could recognize and produce the distinctive grammatical structures of a language and use them effectively in communication. Eisenmann and Summer (2014) also noted that proficiency in English is considered a sufficient condition for successful language learning. On one hand, Sil (2017) reported that effective language learning strategies are generally believed to enhance student's motivation because they can help learners adopt more positive attitudes toward learning. Likewise, Dörnyei and Kubanyiova (2014) asserted that strategies for learning are thought to be effective in fostering student motivation in the classroom. Also, Raba (2017) pointed out that learning strategies encourage student cooperation; this principle deals with teaching practices that promote student cooperation. Research studies indicated that there exists a relationship among learning strategies, English proficiency, and debugging strategies of the students. However, most of them only examined the direct influence of learning strategies on the students' English proficiency. Specifically, Villamizar (2015) showed that there is a significant relationship between language learning strategies and English proficiency among students. The findings indicate that the relevant factor in the effectiveness of the language learning strategies was not the type of strategies used by the learners. The key was the frequency of use of those strategies in the learning pro-

cess. Also, Bosman and Schulze (2018) found that the preference to learn individually correlated most with motivation for achievement in language learning. Thus, in this context, the researcher felt the need to fill in the research gap by conducting a study in the Philippine setting, particularly in Davao City, using a quantitative research approach. Specifically, the researcher used a structural equation model utilizing mediation analysis to understand better the mediating effect of debugging strategies on students' English as determined by language learning strategy, which was found to be scarce. The present study intends to contribute to the limited body of knowledge regarding the students' English language proficiency in the Davao region.

1.1. Review of Significant Literature—This section explores key variables and indicators related to language learning strategies and English proficiency, presenting insights from various studies.

This section explores key variables and indicators related to language learning strategies and English proficiency, presenting insights from various studies.

1.1.1. Language Learning Strategy—Language learning strategies are conscious efforts to achieve systematic and positive learning outcomes (Moskovsky et al., 2013). These include memory, cognitive, compensation, metacognitive, affective, and social strategies (Kean, 2018). Teachers' motivational strategies enhance student engagement and learning attitudes (Sil, 2017; Kabody, 2013). Positive teacher-student relationships foster academic and social engagement (Varga, 2017; Maulana et al., 2013; Rimm-Kaufman Sandilos, 2013).

Effective vocabulary learning strategies, such as training in usage and autonomy, improve language acquisition and independent learning (Brysbaert et al., 2016; de la Garza Harris, 2017). Strategies like mnemonics, repetition, and context-based learning aid retention and comprehension (Heidari, 2019; Wang,

2018).

Cognitive strategies regulate thought processes for problem-solving and goal achievement (Jaleel, 2016; Suyitno, 2017). Metacognitive strategies promote self-regulation and accurate self-assessment, leading to better academic performance (Kuhn Dean, 2014; Norman, 2020). Affective strategies manage emotions to support autonomous and collaborative learning (Gambari et al., 2016; Fjelland, 2020). Social strategies enhance empathetic understanding and peer interaction (Aregu, 2013). English Proficiency

1.1.2. English proficiency—The ability to communicate meaning in spoken and written contexts—is critical for academic success (North Schneider, 1998; Banga, 2016). Proficiency includes indicators such as spoken tasks, comprehension, interaction strategies, and writing tasks.

Weak proficiency hinders comprehension and academic performance (Theresa Irvine, 2015; Martirosyan et al., 2015). Strategies fostering communicative competence improve both language acquisition and content understanding (Chung Pullum, 2015; Mojabi, 2014). Oral communication skills integrate attentive listening and speaking, forming the foundation of effective interaction (Rahman, 2015; Sejdiu, 2017).

Spoken tasks rely on linguistic and socio-cultural knowledge for meaningful communication (Ahmed, 2018; Hymes, 2011). Comprehension, involving linguistic and contextual understanding, is vital for fluency (Chang, 2013). Non-verbal cues enhance conversational clarity and intent (Bjerregaard, 2010; Bavelas Chovil, 2009). Writing tasks enable clear expression and idea development (Nasiri et al., 2016).

Studies link the consistent use of learning strategies with improved proficiency (Villamizar, 2015; Chand, 2015). Individualized learning and teacher support enhance motivation and performance (Bosman Schulze, 2018).

However, some studies note insignificant correlations between specific strategies and proficiency (Ella, 2018; Hayati, 2015).

1.2. Debugging Strategies—Debugging strategies address comprehension and performance errors, fostering metacognitive awareness and critical thinking (Schraw Dennison, 1994; Sil, 2017). They empower learners to transfer knowledge and adapt to new tasks (Sword, 2021; Akin, 2016).

Metacognitive knowledge, combined with language proficiency, significantly impacts reading and comprehension (Guo, 2018; Cartwright, 2015). Executive control and flexibility enable learners to navigate complex texts effectively (Vuong Martin, 2014). Effective language learning and English proficiency depend on strategic approaches encompassing memory, cognitive, affective, and social aspects. Teacher interventions, self-regulated learning, and consistent strategy use significantly enhance outcomes. Emphasis on metacognition and autonomous learning equips students with tools for lifelong language mastery. Effective language learning and English proficiency depend on strategic approaches encompassing memory, cognitive, affective, and social aspects. Teacher interventions, self-regulated learning, and consistent strategy use significantly enhance outcomes. Emphasis on metacognition and autonomous learning equips students with tools for lifelong language mastery.

1.3. Synthesis—Therefore, this portion of the paper provides the researcher with the result of other research to which the present study is related or has some bearing and similarity. More so, the literature showed that language learning strategy, as proposed by Kean (2018), is measured in terms of memory, cognitive, compensation, metacognitive, affective, and social strategies. Meanwhile, as contextualized by North and Schneider (1998), English proficiency is indicated by spoken tasks, comprehension, interaction strategy, quality of spoken performance,

and writing tasks. Also, the researcher established the conceptual framework of the study by explicitly discussing the nature of variables, the choice of population, and the method to answer the research objectives identified. It also provides the basis for the interpretation of data.

1.4. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework—This study was anchored on Chomsky's Nativist Theory of Language Learning (1995), which posits that individuals are born with a specific language-learning area in their brains. The theory suggests that students learn a language much like they learn how to count through repetition and reinforcement. Thus, language arises from stimuli and stimuli response. While this was logical, it fails to explain how new words or phrases come about since children only parrot what they have heard from others. In support, Gilakjani and Ahmadi (2011) postulated that analyzing one's particular learning strategy can be very helpful and beneficial to the student's motivation to be competitive academically by aiding them in becoming more focused and attentive learners, increasing educational success. Discovering this learning style would allow the students to determine their strengths and weaknesses and learn from them. Accordingly, this study contextualizes the idea that developing an effective language learning strategy provides students with skills that will help them become highly proficient in the English language. Such factors would most likely influence the students' motivation to attend class, thus increasing their interest in pursuing English-related courses. As shown in Figure 1, the study consists of two variables: independent variables and dependent variables. The independent variable was language learning strategy, which is the factors an individual consciously exerts to achieve some systematic and enduring positive effect. The measures of learning strategy were memory strategy, or a set of techniques that are designed to help one remember; cognitive strategies or sets of mental processes that are consciously im-

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

plemented to regulate thought processes; compensation strategies or the direct strategies used by learners to 'overcome knowledge limitations in all four skills' in learning and producing a new language; metacognitive strategies or the set of skills that involve thinking about thinking; affective strategies or strategies concerned with managing emotions, both negative and positive;

and social strategies or the social acts that learners employ in order to understand better in the target language. The dependent variable of this study was the English proficiency or the ability of students to use the English language to make and communicate meaning in spoken and written contexts while completing their program of study.

The measures of English proficiency are spoken tasks or the ability to transmit a message that involves the shared understanding between the contexts in which the communication takes place; comprehension or the action or capability of understanding English language concepts; interaction strategy or the confidence and assertiveness in English language skills test; quality of spoken performance or the variation in verbal and nonverbal forms of expression during conversational processes; and writing tasks or the knowledge and abilities related to express-

ing ideas through the written word. Lastly, as defined by Schraw and Dennison (1994), debugging strategies are used to correct comprehension and performance errors.

1.5. Statement of the Problem—The study aimed to determine the mediating effect of debugging strategies on the relationship between language learning strategy and English proficiency of students in cluster 5 schools in Davao City. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

- (1) What is the extent of the language learning strategy of the students in Cluster 5 schools in Davao City in terms of:

- (1) Memory strategy;
 - (2) Cognitive strategies;
 - (3) Compensation Strategies;
 - (4) Metacognitive Strategies;
 - (5) Affective Strategies; and
 - (6) Social Strategies?
- (2) What is the extent of English proficiency of the students in Cluster 5 schools in Davao City in terms of:
- (1) Spoken Tasks;
 - (2) Comprehension;
 - (3) Interaction Strategies;
 - (4) Qualities of Spoken Performance; and
 - (5) Writing Tasks?
- (3) What is the extent of debugging strategies of the students in Cluster 5 schools in Davao City?
- (4) Is there a significant relationship between the language learning strategies, English proficiency, and debugging strategies of the students in Cluster 5 schools in Davao City?
- (5) Does debugging strategies mediate the relationship between language learning strategies and English proficiency of the students in Cluster 5 schools in Davao City?

1.6. *Hypothesis*—The following null hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 level of significance: H01: There is no significant relationship among language learning strategy, English proficiency, and debugging strategies of the students in Cluster 5 schools in Davao City. H02: Debugging strategies do not mediate the relationship between language learning strategies and the English proficiency of the students in Cluster 5 schools in Davao City. Thus, putting into consideration this cited problem situation, the researcher finds it timely to propose this study. The researcher hopes that this study may be beneficial to identified sectors of the academe. This includes the Department of Education (DepEd), policymakers, School administrators, English teachers, and students. The Department of Education. DepEd would benefit from the findings of this study because this can provide them with perspective on how to address the needs of students during the COVID-19 crisis. This can also provide them with an idea of how to help language teachers. The investigation of students' English proficiency was essential because this

may provide a framework for the policymakers to design a curriculum that could maintain higher levels of self-regulated learning among the students. Policy Makers. The finding of this study generates knowledge essential for educational development and policy. With the majority of students likely to experience poor proficiency at some point this school year, this study may provide insights to school administrators so that they could determine what necessary programs were needed to provide resources to help students catch up. From there, it may be able to determine which students may need additional support, and they could reach out to students who struggled with learning and allow students and families to self-identify as needing additional help. English Language Teachers. This research could be important to English language educators because it could help them understand the dimensions that influence language learning strategy as a means of improving English language proficiency. A positive attitude improves motivation, thus increasing performance. This could help teachers realize the

importance of students' abilities. Students. The results could generate facts that are important in providing a competitive learning environment, as well as essential in providing emotional support to the students. Since it was previously known that students' learning motivation has an important effect on students' English language learning and was also an important component of educational and instructional processes, the findings of this study may justify the importance of students' English language learning motivation to students' achievement. Future Researchers. Other researchers would benefit from the result of this study because the findings may provide a framework and model for future research in the context of teacher interaction and English language anxiety. For a more com-

prehensive understanding, the following terms are defined operationally: Language Learning Strategy. This study refers to the independent variable described in terms of the following indicators: memory strategy, cognitive strategies, compensation strategies, metacognitive strategies, affective strategies, and social strategies. English Proficiency. This study refers to the dependent variable described in terms of spoken tasks, comprehension, interaction strategies, qualities of spoken performance, and writing tasks. Debugging Strategies. This study refers to the mediating variable, which was expected to contribute significantly to the relationship between language learning strategies and English proficiency.

2. Methodology

In this chapter, we will outline the processes and steps involved in conducting the study. This will encompass selecting the study's design, identifying the respondents and the sampling method, choosing the research instruments for data collection, and delineating the data analysis process. The researcher employed artificial intelligence methods to meticulously proofread this work during its preparation. Artificial Intelligence (AI) was expressly utilized to enhance the overall quality, coherence, and precision of the manuscript. This methodology is being openly communicated to adhere to ethical norms in research. Leveraging AI for proofreading underscores a commitment to the responsible use of cutting-edge technologies and acknowledges AI's growing role and potential in professional and academic writing.

2.1. Research Design—In this study, a quantitative non-experimental design utilizing the correlational technique of research was the method adopted by the researcher to gather data ideas, facts and information to achieve the main objective of the study. According to Creswell (2013), quantitative research is the systematic empirical investigation of observable phenomena via statistical, mathematical, or computational techniques. It is conclusive in its purpose as it tries to quantify the problem and understand how prevalent it is by looking for projectable results to a larger population. Meanwhile, a quantitative non-experimental descrip-

tive is a scientific method which involves observing and describing the behavior of a subject without influencing it in any way (Curtis, 2016). Meanwhile, according to Myers and Well (2013), descriptive-correlational research examines how the independent variable influences the dependent variable and establishes cause-and-effect relationships between variables. In this study, the researcher would look into the relationship between three variables: language learning strategy, English proficiency, and the students' debugging strategies. Thus, the study's interest was to investigate whether debugging strategies mediate the re-

lationship between language learning strategies and the students' English proficiency.

2.2. *Research Respondents*—The respondents of the study were the 200 junior high school students in Cluster 5 schools in Davao City Division who are officially enrolled for S. Y. 2022-2023. For multiple linear regression, Bujang et al. (2017) suggested a minimum sample size of 300 or more to generate an approximation of estimates with parameters in a survey. The researcher employed stratified random sampling in selecting the respondents from purposively selected schools with strands as the basis for stratification. Stratified random sampling is a type of probability sampling that allows researchers to improve precision relative to simple random sampling wherein the population is divided into non-overlapping groups, or strata, along a relevant dimension such as gender by Salkind, (2020). In this study, certain inclusion criteria were implemented in determining the respondents of the study. The primary consideration of this study was to choose respondents who could provide information to achieve the purpose of this study. For the context of this study, junior high school students enrolled in the schools under Cluster 5 schools in Davao City Division. The researcher preferred to conduct the study in Cluster 5 schools in Davao City

Division because it is one of the clusters that consists of big schools which could provide the needed. Hence, only those students from grades 7-10 students, and who voluntarily signed the ICF. Moreover, the study was delimited only to the nature of the problem based on the research questions.

2.3. *Research Instrument*—In order to gather the data, three adapted survey questionnaires were used. The first tool was about the language learning strategy of the students. This questionnaire was adapted from the study of Kean (2018) and indicated memory strategies, cognitive strategies, compensation strategies, metacognitive strategies, affective strategies, and social strategies. The Cronbach coefficient value for this instrument is 0.900, indicating high reliability and consistency. This questionnaire was subjected to content validity by a panel of experts to test its validity and reliability. In the manner of answering the questionnaire, the items were modified so that they may suit the context of this answer and be answerable using a 5-Likert scale: 5—Strongly Agree 4—Agree 3—Moderately Agree 2—Disagree 1—Strongly Disagree. As a guide in determining the extent of language learning strategy, the researcher made use of the range of means, descriptions, and interpretations presented below:

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	Language learning strategy is always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	Language learning strategy is oftentimes manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	Language learning strategy is sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	Language learning strategy is seldom manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	Language learning strategy is never manifested.

The second instrument was the English proficiency Scale by North and Schneider (1998) with domains namely spoken tasks, comprehension, interaction strategies, qualities of spoken performance, and writing tasks. The reliability of the original scale was obtained with a Cronbach’s alpha value of 0.92. This questionnaire was subjected for content validity by a panel of experts and underwent pilot testing to test its validity and reliability In the man-

ner of answering the questionnaire, the items were modified so that they may suit the context of this and be answerable using the 5-Likert scale: 5–Strongly Agree 4–Agree 3–Moderately Agree 2–Disagree 1–Strongly Disagree. As a guide in determining the English proficiency of the students, the researcher made use of the range of means, descriptions, and interpretations as presented below:

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	English proficiency is always evident.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	English proficiency is oftentimes evident.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	English proficiency is sometimes evident.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	English proficiency is seldom evident.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	English proficiency is never evident.

The third part is about the debugging strategies of the students. The questionnaire is adopted from Schraw and Dennison’s (1994) Metacognitive Awareness Inventory Scale. The reliability of the new scale obtained Cronbach’s

alpha value of 0.978, described as excellent, indicating high reliability and consistency among the items. The questionnaire made use of a 5-point Likert scale which was determined based on the following range of mean:

Range of Mean	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	Debugging strategies are always evident.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	Debugging strategies are oftentimes evident.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	Debugging strategies are sometimes evident.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	Debugging strategies are seldom evident.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	Debugging strategies are never evident.

A panel of experts validated the content of these questionnaires, which underwent pilot testing to test their validity and reliability.

The experts’ comments, corrections, and suggestions were incorporated into the final revisions of the questionnaires.

2.4. Data Gathering Procedure—Steps were undergone by the researcher in conducting the study after the validation of the research questionnaire. Steps were undergone by the

researcher in conducting the study after the validation of the research questionnaire. Permission to Conduct the Study. The researcher secured permission to conduct the study and the endorse-

ment from the Dean of the Graduate School in Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City. The endorsement letter from the Dean of the Graduate School in Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City, was attached to the permission letters to be endorsed to the school principals of the selected public secondary schools in Cluster 5 schools in Davao City Division. The letters were personally brought by the researchers to the principals of the schools where the study was conducted. The researcher first appeared at the office of the principals in the second week of November 2022. However, the researcher was not able to receive the approval from the respective office due to the busy schedules of the principals. So, the researcher came back in the second week of December 2022. The approval from the respective offices was then granted. After which, the researcher proceeded to the distribution and retrieval of the survey questionnaires. Distribution and Retrieval of the Questionnaire. The researcher proceeded to the distribution of the research instrument to the respondents after the approval to conduct the study. The study was conducted in the second quarter of S.Y. 2022-2023. Upon the distribution of the questionnaires, the benefits of the survey were briefly discussed and explained to the identified respondents of the study. For the administration of the questionnaire, the researcher distributed the questionnaires simultaneously. The respondents of the study were given enough testing time for the questionnaires to be finished. After this, the data collected were subjected to quantitative analysis. Collation and Statistical Treatment of Data. After the data retrieval of the questionnaire, the scores of each respondent were tallied to organize the data per indicator. After this, each score was subjected to descriptive and inferential analysis using SPSS.

2.5. Ethical Considerations—The researcher promptly observed the protocols deemed necessary as the standard guidelines in carrying out the research study following

the study protocol assessment criteria, particularly in managing the population and data. The survey questionnaires with supporting authors were submitted for further evaluation. After the approval from the Ethics Committee, the researcher proceeded to the next phase of the study. Informed Consent. The researcher asked for the permission of respondents through a written informed consent. They were properly informed about the purpose of the study, and ample explanations were given to them for a better understanding of the reason for their participation so that they could choose whether to participate or not. It was made clear that respondents' involvement in the study is voluntary. If ever they would refuse to participate, they were not forced by the researcher. Besides, the researcher was cautious in assure the respondents' psychological well-being. A written permission from the respondents were secured from them. The researcher informed the respondents that the study aimed to conduct a study on the factors that hinder/promote the student's English proficiency as determined by their language learning strategies and debugging strategies and may contribute to the enhancement. Vulnerability of Research Participants. The respondents of the study are junior high school students, so they are considered vulnerable since all of them are not yet in legal age, and they are considered highly vulnerable in the psychological aspect. The researcher emphasized that the survey was set at the respondents' convenience. Also, the researcher protected the confidentiality of the information disclosed. Privacy and Confidentiality. This study observed the Data Privacy Act of 2012, wherein the researcher assured that the data could not be traced back to the participants, who were the real source of information, to protect the identities of the respondents. Moreover, the researcher assured that no personal data would be shared without the consent of the respondents. Thus, to ensure that no personal data would be exposed,

access was limited to the researcher alone. To protect the privacy of the respondents, it was assured that the researcher was the only person who could access the survey results. After the necessary data was collected, the researcher permanently disposed of the survey result to ensure that data could not be traced back to the respondents, who were the real source of information. Risk, Benefits and Safety - In administering the survey questionnaires, the researcher fully disclosed to the respondents the nature of their participation and explained thoroughly and properly the purpose and benefits of the study as well as the confidentiality of their responses as stated in the online survey questionnaire. The respondents, without restrictions, will be able to ask questions related to the study. Further, the researcher ensured that the respondents were not subjected to harm in any way whatsoever. Moreover, the questionnaire and interview guide that were used in this study did not contain any degrading or unacceptable statements offensive to the respondents of the study. Likewise, this study is designed purely to collect academic information related to the study, and they were not asked for personal information. To minimize inconvenience, the researcher made sure that the respondents were given ample time to answer the survey questionnaires. The respondents were given the freedom not to answer questions that made them feel any psychological or emotional distress, and they would be free to withdraw as respondents to the study if they felt that they could not discuss the information that was being asked of them. Justice. To avoid impartiality in choosing the respondents, the researcher regarded all respondents equally regardless if they would be respondents in the survey. The researcher was not prejudiced in choosing the respondents of the study. Anybody who fits the qualifications of being bonafide enrolled learners in the purposively selected schools. During the conduct of the study, the researcher made certain to respect the respondents by interrupting as little time as possible to the routine of the respondents. To compensate for the time spent during data gathering, the researcher gave tokens of appreciation to the respondents. This token was an assortment of souvenirs. The tokens were sent via courier, and these were sealed carefully in a package. Transparency. To provide transparency in this study, any type of communication in relation to the research was done with honesty and transparency. To safeguard the welfare of the respondents, the researcher properly implemented the methods that are discussed to use in this study. All the necessary documents that supported the data analysis were included. Importantly, the researcher described the extent of the involvement of the respondents in this study and shared how the researcher maintained objectivity in analyzing data and presentation of the results of the study. Qualification of the Researcher. The researcher ensured that the responses of the respondents were not influenced by any other factor like the conflict of interest. The findings of the study could be accessed by the respondents and parents, and school administrators of the participating schools because the information would be made available as long as they followed proper protocol to protect the anonymity of the respondents. The researcher also acknowledged the effort of every person who contributed to the success of the study; the Division of Davao City was given a furnished copy of the research results so that the respondents could access them and use them for learning and further study. Adequacy of Facilities. The researcher engaged the respondents in a conducive environment and learning materials that were ample and available during the study, which was done within the time set by the researcher. The accuracy of gathering data from the respondents was ensured by encoding the ratings of the respondents properly during the day when the researcher was not too tired to do them to avoid errors in encoding. Also,

the analysis and results gathered were proficient and aligned, which serves as a primary basis for adequacy. Community Involvement. It was a good practice to have community involvement during every phase of research, from planning to reporting. Hence, the researcher planned to share the findings generated with the community and community involvement was accorded primacy in making decisions about the research agenda, appropriate method to apply in their context, and use of the results or findings. The findings of this study would then be shared back with the community through gatherings, fora, and conferences.

2.6. *Data Analysis*—The following were the statistical tools utilized by the researcher in processing the gathered data: Mean. This was

useful in characterizing the language learning strategies, English proficiency, and debugging strategies of the students. Mean, and standard deviation are descriptive statistics that tend to measure how the score is clustered and scattered, respectively. Pearson Product Moment Correlation. This was utilized to determine the significance of the relationship among language learning strategies, English proficiency, and debugging strategies of the students. It is a statistical measure of the strength of a linear relationship between paired data. The Structural Equation Model through Mediation Analysis was applied to evaluate the mediating effect of debugging strategies on the relationship between language learning strategies and students' English proficiency.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results generated from the data gathered. It is sequenced based on the objectives of the study, as presented in the first chapter. Thus, it presents the extent of Debugging Strategies, Language Learning Strategies and English Proficiency of the students in Cluster 5 Schools in Davao City; the significant relationship among Debugging Strategies, Language Learning Strategies and English Proficiency of the students in Cluster 5 Schools in Davao City; and the mediating effect of Debugging Strategies on Language Learning Strategy in relation to English Proficiency of the students in Cluster 5 Schools in Davao City.

3.1. *Language Learning Strategies of the Students in Cluster 5 Schools in Davao City – Metacognitive Strategy*—The language learning strategies in terms of metacognitive strategy reflect a category mean of 3.59, described as extensive, interpreted as oftentimes manifested by the junior high school students in Cluster 5 Schools in Davao City. The mean ratings of the

different items range from 3.20 to 3.89. Specifically, the item, planning my schedule so I will have enough time to study English, has a mean rating of 3.20, described as moderately extensive, interpreted as an item sometimes manifested. The item, trying to find out how to be a better learner of English, reflects a mean of 3.89, described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes manifested.

The findings denote that the junior high school students in Cluster 5 Schools in Davao City oftentimes manifested the ability to manipulate and take control of their own thinking ability. The extensive rating on this domain is due to the fact that the students were able

to retrieve and deploy that strategy in a similar but new context because they were able to use metacognitive strategies. This finding supports the study of Kuhn and Dean (2014). Adding more, the students were able to perform executive control involving monitoring and self-

Table 1. Extent of Language Learning Strategies of the Students in Terms of Metacognitive Strategy

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Trying to find as many ways as I can to use my English.	3.67	Extensive
Noticing my English mistakes and use that information to help me do better.	3.80	Extensive
Paying attention when someone is speaking English.	3.80	Extensive
Trying to find out how to be a better learner of English.	3.89	Extensive
Planning my schedule so I will have enough time to study English.	3.20	Moderately Extensive
Looking for people I can talk to in English.	3.25	Moderately Extensive
Looking for opportunities to read as much as possible in English.	3.40	Extensive
Having clear goals for improving my English skills.	3.64	Extensive
Thinking about my progress in learning English.	3.67	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.59	Extensive

regulation. Students who feel over - or under-confident about a subject are far less likely to review and work on extra problems than students who know their knowledge level. This finding agrees with Bergstresser (2015).

3.2. *Social Strategy*—With respect to social strategy, it reflects a category mean of 3.55, described as extensive, which is interpreted as a language learning strategy that is oftentimes manifested by junior high school students. It

This implies that the social acts that learners employ to better understand the target language are often manifested by junior high school students. In the context of the study, the respondents were able to use the social domain to increase their interaction and empathetic understanding as they occur among and between other students and teachers. The finding supports the view of Etxebarria et al. (2012).

can be seen that the mean ratings of the different items range from 3.43 to 3.67. The item, Practicing English with other students, has a mean rating of 3.43, described as extensive and interpreted as an item oftentimes manifested. Whereas the item Asking the other person to slow down or say it again if I do not understand something in English has a mean rating of 3.67, described as extensive and interpreted as an item that is oftentimes manifested.

3.3. *Cognitive Strategies*—Adding on, this dimension has a category mean of 3.46, described as extensive, which means that this particular domain of language learning strategies of junior high school students is oftentimes manifested. Adding on, the mean ratings of the different items range from 3.13 to 3.77. Specifically, the item, Trying not to translate word-for-word, shows a mean rating of 3.13, described

Table 2. Extent of Language Learning Strategies of the Students in Terms of Social Strategy

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Asking the other person to slow down or say it again if I do not understand something in English.	3.67	Extensive
Asking English speakers to correct me when I talk.	3.56	Extensive
Practicing English with other students.	3.43	Extensive
Asking for help from English speakers.	3.48	Extensive
Asking questions in English.	3.53	Extensive
Trying to learn about the culture of English speakers.	3.67	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.55	Extensive

as moderately extensive, interpreted as an item sometimes manifested. The item, Practicing the sounds of English, reflects a mean rating of 3.77, described as extensive and interpreted as an item oftentimes manifested. The study’s results indicate that the sets of mental processes that are consciously implemented to regulate thought processes and content in order to achieve goals are often manifested by the junior high school students in Cluster 5 Schools in Davao City.

Table 3. Extent of Language Learning Strategies of the Students in Terms of Cognitive Strategy

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Saying or writing new English words several times.	3.51	Extensive
Trying to talk like native English speakers.	3.52	Extensive
Practicing the sounds of English.	3.77	Extensive
Using the English words I know in different ways.	3.45	Extensive
Trying not to translate word-for-word.	3.13	Moderately Extensive
Making summaries of information that I hear or read in English.	3.39	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean	3.46	Extensive

The findings showed that junior high school students were able to use cognitive strategies such as repetition, organizing new language, summarizing meaning, guessing meaning from context, and using imagery for memorization in order to learn more successfully. This result supports the findings of Liu and Lin (2016). Also, the findings showed that students oftentimes exhibit the ability to think strategically and to solve problems, set goals, organize ideas, and evaluate what is known and not known. This is in consonance with the view of Jaleel (2016).

3.4. *Compensation Strategy*—This particular domain of language learning strategy of junior high school students reflects an extensive category mean of 3.41 which means that it is oftentimes manifested. Notably, the mean ratings of the different items range from 3.15

to 3.55. The table further reveals that the item Reading English without looking up every new word has a mean rating of 3.15, described as moderately extensive, interpreted as an item that is sometimes manifested. Meanwhile, the item, understanding unfamiliar English words by making guesses, reflects a mean rating of 3.55, described as extensive, interpreted as an item oftentimes manifested by the junior high school students in Cluster 5 Schools in Davao City.

Table 4. Extent of Language Learning Strategies of the Students in Terms of Compensation Strategy

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Understanding unfamiliar English words by making guesses.	3.55	Extensive
Using gestures when I can't think of a word during a conversation in English.	3.51	Extensive
Making up new words if I do not know the right ones in English.	3.49	Extensive
Reading English without looking up every new word.	3.15	Moderately Extensive
Trying to guess what the other person will say next in English.	3.48	Extensive
Using a word or phrase that means the same thing if I can't think of an English word.	3.31	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean	3.41	Extensive

The results suggest that the direct strategies used by learners to 'overcome knowledge limitations in all four skills' in learning and producing a new language is oftentimes manifested. This finding supports the study of Kean (2018) that compensation strategies 'help learners to overcome knowledge limitations in all four skills. This is very relevant to language learners because, as learners, they may lack knowledge about language to some extent. Thus, Compensation strategies have come to the rescue to help the learners to overcome their problems in learning a new language. In other words, we may say that compensation strategies are crucial for language learners. Chee (2014) also asserted that these strategies may be among the most important strategies for beginning and intermediate

language learners. Compensation strategies are 'also useful for more expert language users who occasionally do not know an expression.

3.5. *Memory Strategy*—Consequently, the dimension of memory strategy is described as moderately extensive, with a category mean of 3.36. This means that the learning strategy of junior high school students is sometimes manifested. The mean rating of the different items ranges from 2.88 to 3.77. The item, Use flashcards to remember new English words, reflects a mean rating of 2.88, described as moderately extensive, and interpreted as a learning strategy for grade 10 students is sometimes manifested. Furthermore, the item Thinking of relationships between what I already know and new things I learn in English has a mean rating of 3.77, de-

scribed as extensive, interpreted as oftentimes manifested. The result suggests that techniques designed to help students remember are sometimes manifested. The students were able to link the word with some previously learned knowledge, and their goal is organization and consolidation.

Table 5. Extent of Language Learning Strategies of the Students in Terms of Memory Strategy

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Thinking of relationships between what I already know and new things I learn in English.	3.77	Extensive
Using new English words in a sentence so I can remember them.	3.53	Extensive
Connecting the sound of a new English word and an image or picture of the word to help me remember the word	3.53	Extensive
Remembering a new English word by making a mental picture of a situation in which the word might be used	3.49	Moderately Extensive
Using rhymes to remember new English words.	3.26	Moderately Extensive
Using flashcards to remember new English words.	2.88	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean	3.36	Moderately Extensive

This finding is in congruence with the view of Wang (2018). More so, the finding agrees with Heidari (2019) that memory strategy could be used as mnemonics by learners to make mental linkages that would allow new words to enter, remain, and be retrieved for communication in long-term memory.

3.6. *Affective Strategy*—In particular, this dimension has a category mean of 3.32, interpreted as moderately extensive, which means that in terms of affective strategy, the learning strategy of the grade 10 students is sometimes manifested. The mean ratings of the items range

from 2.79 to 3.72. The item, writing down my feelings in a language-learning diary, reflects a mean rating of 2.79, described as moderately extensive, interpreted as sometimes manifested. Meanwhile, the items, encouraging myself to speak English even when I am afraid of making a mistake, reflect the mean rating of 3.72, described as extensive and interpreted as an item is oftentimes manifested. The result suggests that the learning strategies concerned with managing emotions, both negative and positive, are sometimes manifested among the respondents.

The finding is in consonance with the study of Fjelland (2020) that effective strategies enable humans to perform in everyday life in the spheres of personal, social, and occupational activities. These mental processes include the

ability to attend to things in a selective and focused way, to concentrate over some time, to learn new information and skills, to plan, to determine strategies for actions, to execute them, to comprehend language, to use verbal skills

Table 6. Extent of Language Learning Strategy of the Students in Terms of Affective Strategy

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Trying to relax whenever I feel afraid of English.	3.63	Extensive
Encouraging myself to speak English even when I am afraid of making a mistake.	3.72	Extensive
Giving myself a reward or treat when I do well in English.	3.28	Moderately Extensive
Noticing if I am tense or nervous when I am studying or using English	3.43	Extensive
Writing down my feelings in a language-learning diary.	2.79	Moderately Extensive
Talking to someone else about how I feel when I am learning English.	3.06	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean	3.32	Moderately Extensive

for communication and self-expression, and to retain information and manipulate it to solve complex problems.

3.7. *The Summary of The Extent of Language Learning Strategies of The Junior High School Students in Cluster 5 Schools in Davao City*—Lastly, Table 7 shows the summary of the extent of language learning strategies of the junior high school students in Cluster 5 schools in Davao City. The overall mean of the language learning strategies is 3.45, described as extensive. It means that the learning strategy of the junior high school students in Cluster 5 schools in Davao City is oftentimes manifested. This suggests that junior high school

students oftentimes manifest the factors that are consciously exerted by an individual to achieve some systematic and enduring positive effect. The results showed that the students were able to use the learning strategies that enhanced their motivation which helped them adopt more positive attitudes towards learning. This finding is in consonance with the finding of Sil (2017). According to Kabody (2013), a teacher must have the knowledge of effective motivational teaching strategies because they play the most significant role in the academic environment, engaging the learners and pursuing them in the long journey of their learning.

In addition, the result is in agreement with the view of Gusti (2016) that learning strategy is the activities utilized by language learners in order to make their learning easier and more effective and can be used or transferred to other situations related to language learning. These strategies could serve as learning tools for students in order for them to acquire vocabulary and become responsible for their own learning. With

the skill and knowledge of vocabulary learning strategies, learners can learn new vocabulary without the teacher’s presence (Bas Beyhan, 2019). Also, the result agrees with Manyak et al. (2019) that learners may utilize different learning strategies and should be taught how to use them.

3.8. *English Proficiency of the Junior High School Students in Cluster 5 Schools in*

Table 7. Summary on the Extent of Language Learning Strategies of Junior High School Students in Cluster 5 Schools in Davao City

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Memory Strategy	3.36	Moderately Extensive
Cognitive Strategy	3.46	Extensive
Compensation Strategy	3.41	Extensive
Metacognitive Strategy	3.59	Extensive
Affective Strategy	3.32	Moderately Extensive
Social Strategy	3.55	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.45	Extensive

Davao City—Writing Tasks. Correspondingly, the writing tasks of the junior high school students reveal a category mean of 3.80, described as extensive, which means that this particular indicator of English language proficiency is oftentimes observed by the junior high school students in Cluster 5 schools in Davao City. The mean item ratings range from 3.68 to 3.96.

Table 8. Extent of English Proficiency of the Junior High School Students in Terms of Written Tasks

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Can fill in uncomplicated forms with personal details, name, address, nationality, and marital status.	3.80	Extensive
Can write simple notes to friends	3.96	Extensive
Can write personal letters to a friend, host, etc. Giving and asking for news.	3.68	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.80	Extensive

The item Can write personal letters to a friend, host, etc. Giving and asking for news has a mean rating of 3.67, described as extensive, which means that this particular descriptor on English language proficiency of junior high school students is oftentimes manifested, while the item, can write simple notes to friends, has a mean of 3.95 described as extensive which means that this particular descriptor on English language proficiency is oftentimes manifested. As such, the result implies that the knowledge and abilities related to expressing ideas through the written word are oftentimes manifested. The findings showed that the students perceived writ-

ing as a way of communicating ideas and messages orally. Writing helps individuals develop their vocabulary and grammar skills and then better their writing skills. The finding supports the view of Nasiri et al. (2016). Also, the students could express their emotions and ideas, say stories, request, talk, discuss, and show the various functions of language. The result is congruent with the view of Efrizal (2012). In addition, the result agrees with the view of Mazouzi (2013) that individuals should have enough English-speaking ability to communicate easily and effectively with other people.

3.9. *Comprehension*—With respect to school students in Cluster 5 Schools in Davao City is oftentimes manifested. It can be seen that the mean ratings of the different items range from 3.26 to 3.65.

Table 9. Extent of English Proficiency of the Students in Terms of Comprehension

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Understanding clear, standard speech on familiar matters directed at him/her, provided he or she can ask for repetition or reformulation from time to time.	3.39	Moderately Extensive
Understanding keywords and phrases in conversations between native speakers and using them to follow the topics.	3.65	Extensive
Keeping language clear and simple, as far as possible, avoiding the use of idiomatic expressions and complex information structuring in order for him/her to understand.	3.41	Extensive
Having a good deal of paraphrasing and explanation when the speaker is attempting to convey or obtain detailed information in order to be able to understand.	3.26	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean	3.43	Extensive

The item, having a good deal of paraphrasing and explanation when the speaker is attempting to convey or obtain detailed information in order to be able to understand, has a mean rating of 3.26, which is described as moderate and interpreted as sometimes manifested. Whereas the item Understanding keywords and phrases in conversations between native speakers and using them to follow the topics has a mean of 3.65, described as high and interpreted as an item that is oftentimes evident. This implies that the action or capability of understanding English language concepts is oftentimes manifested. The finding supports the view of Alam (2013) that comprehension of the systems of language is crucial and as equally as important as the development of fluency and contextual accuracy. Also, the result agrees with Rahman

(2015) that listening attentively and speaking are oral communication skills that are both life-long activities and probably the most important communication tool. Both are integrated skills that support the development of each other. The integration of attentive listening and speaking skills is termed oral communication skills because listening can be developed indirectly by integrating it into speaking (Ellis, 2011).

3.10. *Interaction Strategy* —This dimension has a category mean of 3.36, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as English proficiency of junior high school students is sometimes manifested. Adding on, looking at the mean ratings of the different items, they range from 3.29 to 3.44. The item, being conscious of when he or she mixes up tenses, words, and expressions and tries to self-correct, reflects

a mean rating of 3.29, described as moderately extensive, and interpreted as an item that is sometimes manifested. The items, using a simple word meaning something similar to the concept he or she wants to convey and invites corrections, have a mean rating of 3.44, described as extensive and interpreted as items oftentimes

manifested. The results imply that confidence and assertiveness in English language skills test is sometimes manifested among the junior high school students in Cluster 5 Schools in Davao City. The students show the qualities of being assertive and attentive.

Table 10. The extent of English Proficiency of the Students in Terms of Interaction Strategy

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Joining in a conversation appropriately.	3.40	Extensive
Repeating back part of what someone has said to confirm mutual understanding and help keep the development of ideas on course.	3.39	Moderately Extensive
Asking for clarification about keywords not understood using stock phrases.	3.38	Moderately Extensive
Rehearsing and trying out new combinations and expressions, inviting feedback.	3.31	Moderately Extensive
Using a simple word means something similar to the concept he or she wants to convey and invites corrections.	3.44	Extensive
Defining features of something concrete so he or she can't remember the word	3.33	Moderately Extensive
Being conscious of when he or she mixes up tenses, words, and expressions and tries to self-correct.	3.29	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean	3.36	Moderately Extensive

The students also exhibit the desire to pay attention to a variety of stimuli, which takes away from the overall attention given to a specific stimulus. Dividing listening is equated with multitasking and the desire to focus on multiple agendas during a conversation process. These findings support the view of Engen (2012). This result also agrees with Brownell (2018) that if a stimulus is never consciously attended to, it will not become part of the listener's memory. Listeners tend to focus on what he/she wants

to hear or expect to hear. Ideas need to be connected to what is already known if they are to be placed in one's memory.

3.11. *Spoken Tasks* —In particular, this dimension has a category mean of 3.68, interpreted as extensive, which means that in terms of spoken tasks, the English proficiency of the students in Cluster 5 Schools in Davao City is oftentimes manifested. The mean ratings of the items range from 3.00 to 3.53.

Table 11. The extent of English Proficiency of the Students in Terms of Spoken Tasks

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Using public transport: buses, trains, and taxis for basic information, asking and giving directions, and buying tickets.	3.31	Moderately Extensive
Coping with less routine situations in shops, offices, tanks, e.g., asking for a larger size, returning an unsatisfactory purchase	3.38	Moderately Extensive
Negotiating a price, e.g., for a second-hand car or bike.	3.33	Moderately Extensive
Getting along the information needed from a tourist office, as long as it is of a straightforward, non-specialized nature.	3.21	Moderately Extensive
Making a phone call to book a hotel, order a book, etc., coping with the switchboard, wrong numbers, bad lines, etc., and delivering a short prepared statement.	3.00	Moderately Extensive
Entering unprepared into conversations on familiar topics.	3.23	Moderately Extensive
Make an introduction and use basic greeting and leave-taking expressions.	3.53	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.28	Moderately Extensive

The item, making a phone call to book a hotel, order a book, etc., coping with the switchboard, wrong numbers, bad lines, etc. and delivering a short prepared statement reflects a mean rating of 3.00, described as moderately extensive, interpreted as the item is sometimes manifested. Meanwhile, the item, making an introduction and using basic greeting and leave-taking expressions, shows a mean rating of 3.53, described as extensive and interpreted as an item that is oftentimes manifested by the junior high school students in Cluster 5 Schools in Davao City. The result suggests that the transmission of a message that involves the shared understanding between the contexts in which the communication takes place is oftentimes manifested. The finding is in consonance with the view of Ahmed (2018) that spoken skills as both the knowledge of the linguistic and not

linguistic rules of communication and the skill to use such knowledge effectively and appropriately in real-life situations for the purpose of fulfilling communicative goals. In a similar view, Hymes (2011) noted that the knowledge of language structure and sociocultural rules are both important in language acquisition. Accordingly, an individual acquires knowledge of language not only as grammatical but also as appropriate.

3.12. Quality of Spoken Performance—In particular, the quality of spoken performance reflects a mean of 3.26, interpreted as moderately extensive, which means that the English proficiency of the students in Cluster 5 Schools in Davao City is sometimes manifested. The mean ratings among the aspects of the quality of spoken tasks range from 3.11 to 3.43. The item, Using reasonably accurately a repertoire

of frequently used routines and patterns associated with more predictable situations, has a mean of 3.11, described as moderately extensive, which means that this particular descriptor of English proficiency is sometimes manifested. Notably, the item, Using simple structures correctly but still systematically making basic mistakes, reflects a mean rating of 3.43, described as extensive, which means that in this item, English language proficiency is oftentimes manifested. This suggests that the variation in verbal and nonverbal forms of expression during conversational processes is sometimes manifested

among the respondents in Cluster 5 Schools in Davao City. This finding is in accordance with the statement of Bjerregaard (2010) that non-verbal communication is a collection of expressions and body language an individual consciously or unconsciously expresses to anyone watching. These behaviors include facial expressions, postures, eye behaviors, tone of voice, and gestures. Nonverbal behaviors are of central importance to the expression of emotions. These non-verbal cues help regulate the flow of conversation, facilitate turn-taking, provide feedback, and convey subtle meanings.

Table 12. Extent of English Proficiency of the Students in Terms of Quality of Spoken Performance

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Linking a series of shorter, discrete simple elements into a connected discourse.	3.18	Moderately Extensive
Having a repertoire of basic language that enables him or her to deal with everyday situations with predictable content, though he or she will generally have to compromise the message and search for words.	3.21	Moderately Extensive
Having sufficient vocabulary to conduct routine, everyday transactions involving familiar situations and topics.	3.33	Moderately Extensive
Using reasonably accurately a repertoire of frequently used routines and patterns associated with more predictable situations.	3.11	Moderately Extensive
Using simple structures correctly but still systematically making basic mistakes.	3.43	Extensive
Showing stress and intonation are very foreign but can be followed nearly.	3.18	Moderately Extensive
Beginning to show awareness of the rules and conventions governing social interaction but still frequently fails to recognize nuances in tone of voice and to respond appropriately.	3.36	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean	3.26	Moderately Extensive

In addition, Plumb (2013) emphasized that in normal conversation, there are few interruptions or long pauses, and the distribution of participation is consistent, though skewed toward higher-status members.

3.13. *Summary of the English Proficiency of the Students in Cluster 5 Schools in Davao City*—Lastly, Table 13 shows that the English proficiency of junior high school students reflects an overall mean of 3.43, described as extensive. This shows that the English profi-

ciency of the students is oftentimes manifested. Adding more, results on the table show that English proficiency in terms of written tasks acquired the highest mean score of 3.80, described as extensive, interpreted as a domain oftentimes manifested by the respondents. Meanwhile, English proficiency in terms of qualities of spoken performance acquired the lowest mean score of 3.26, described as moderately extensive, interpreted as a domain oftentimes manifested.

Table 13. Summary of the English Proficiency of the Students in Cluster 5 Schools in Davao City

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Spoken Tasks	3.28	Moderately Extensive
Comprehension	3.43	Extensive
Interaction Strategy	3.36	Moderately Extensive
Qualities of Spoken Performance	3.26	Moderately Extensive
Written Tasks	3.80	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.43	Extensive

The result suggests that the ability of students to use the English language to make and communicate meaning in spoken and written contexts while completing their program of study is oftentimes evident among the respondents. This finding is similar to the study of Attaprechakul (2013) that student’s English Language proficiency could play a substantial role among pupils studying English as a second language, and attitude implies favorable or unfavorable evaluative reaction towards something, events, programs, and other exhibited in an individual’s beliefs, feelings, emotions or intended behaviors. Similarly, the result also agrees with Rafiu and Nwalo’s (2016) view that language proficiency is the ability of an individual to speak or perform in an acquired language. According to Banga (2016), students’ success in

school depends largely on their proficiency in the language of instruction. If students’ language proficiency is low, they will likely not perform. Conversely, Oribabor (2014) asserted that low academic English language proficiency levels can be an obstacle to academic success and full participation in academic content.

3.14. *Debugging Strategies of the Students in Cluster 5 Schools in Davao City*—Table 14 shows the extent of students’ debugging strategies in Cluster 5 Schools in Davao City. The overall mean is 3.69, which is described as extensive. The mean ratings of the items range from 3.45 to 4.02. The item asking others for help when I don’t understand something reflects a mean rating of 3.45, which is described as extensive and interpreted as an item that is often evident.

Table 14. Summary Table on the Extent of Debugging Strategies of Students in Cluster 5 Schools in Davao City

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Asking others for help when I don't understand something.	3.45	Extensive
Changing strategies when I fail to understand.	3.66	Extensive
Re-evaluating my assumptions when I get confused.	3.78	Extensive
Stopping and going back over new information that is not clear.	4.02	Extensive
Stopping and rereading when I get confused.	3.55	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.69	Extensive

Meanwhile, the item, Stopping and going back over new information that is not clear, shows a mean rating of 4.02, described as extensive and interpreted as an item on this domain is oftentimes evident. The result suggests that the strategies used to correct comprehension and performance errors are oftentimes evident. The finding is in consonance with the view of Sil (2017) that teachers' use of motivational strategies is generally believed to enhance student motivation because it can help learners adopt more positive attitudes toward learning. Also, the result agrees with Savas and Gurel (2014) that teachers who were able to organize the learning environment effectively were able to manage their classroom better and positively affect student achievement and behaviors. Likewise, the finding is congruent with the view of Al'Omairi and Al Balushi (2015) that attention allows us to plan or preview, monitor, and regulate our thoughts and actions. Through this, students can focus on the meaning and significance of new information. An individual cannot understand, learn, or remember what we do not first attend to.

3.15. *Relationship among Language Learning Strategies, English Proficiency and*

Debugging Strategies of Students in Cluster 5 Schools in Davao City—The results of the analysis of the relationship among language learning strategies, English proficiency, and debugging strategies in Cluster 5 Schools in Davao City are presented. Bivariate correlation analysis using Pearson product-moment correlation was utilized to determine the relationship among the variables mentioned. Table 15 shows that language learning strategies have a significant positive relationship with the English proficiency of the students with a p-value of .000, which is less than the .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .523, p < 0.05$). This means that as the language learning strategies are expanded, the English proficiency of the students also significantly changes. This leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between language learning strategies and the English proficiency of the students. The findings are in consonance with the study of Chand (2015) that direct teaching of some of these learning strategies by academic advisors potentially increases the use of them across a broad population of students, not solely those deemed at risk of attrition or those with probationary status.

Table 15. Relationship among Language Learning Strategies, English Proficiency, and Debugging Strategies of Students in Cluster 5 Schools in Davao City

Variables	English Proficiency	Debugging Strategies
Language Learning Strategies	0.523** 0.000	0.749** 0.000
English Proficiency	1	0.842** 0.000

**Significant @ p<0.05

On the one hand, the result shows that the relationship between language learning strategies and debugging strategies of the students has a significant positive relationship with a p-value of .00 that is less than the alpha set at .05 ($r = 0.749$ $p < 0.05$). This means that if the extent of language learning strategies changes, the extent of debugging strategies of the students also significantly changes. This leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between language learning strategies and students' debugging strategies. The findings are in consonance with the study of Villamizar (2015), which states that the relevant factor in the effectiveness of language learning strategies was not the type of strategies used by learners. The key was the frequency of use of those strategies in the learning process. Moreover, the result shows that the relationship between debugging strategies has a significant positive relationship with the English proficiency of the students with a p-value of .000 that is less than the alpha set at .05 ($r = 0.842$ $p < .05$). This means that if the extent of debugging strategies changes, English proficiency of the students also significantly changes. This leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between debugging strategies has a significant positive relationship with the English proficiency of the students of the Cluster 5 Schools in Davao City. This finding is parallel to the findings of a study conducted by Naim-

nule and Corebima (2018), which found that debugging strategies are essential for successful learning because they enable individuals to direct their own cognitive skills toward a higher level. Also, Zoupidis et al. (2016) noted that the idea that metacognition includes noticing how one thinks and learns shows that metacognition can foster an active thinking process.

3.16. Mediating Effect of Debugging Strategies on Language Learning Strategies and English Proficiency of the Students in Cluster 5 Schools in Davao City—Results in Table 16 show the mediating effect of debugging strategies on the relationship between language learning strategies and English proficiency of the students in Cluster 5 Schools in Davao City. As shown in the table, the total effect of language learning strategies as the independent variable on the English proficiency of the students in Cluster 5 Schools in Davao City, which is this study's dependent variable, is significant, as evident by the estimated value of 0.751 and $p < 0.05$. On the one hand, it could be seen in the table that the direct effect of language learning strategies on the English proficiency of the students in Cluster 5 Schools in Davao City is significant, as indicated by an estimated value of 0.393, $p < 0.05$. Lastly, language learning strategies on the English proficiency of the students in Cluster 5 Schools in Davao City with debugging strategies as a mediator is significant, as indicated by the estimated value of 0.358 and $p < 0.05$. There-

fore, it could be said that partial mediation took place. Hence, the null hypothesis of debugging strategies does not mediate the relationship between the English proficiency of the students in Cluster 5 Schools in Davao City is rejected.

Table 16. Mediating Effect of Debugging Strategies on Language Learning Strategies and English Proficiency of the Students in Cluster 5 Schools in Davao City

Effect Type	Path	Estimate	Std. Error	z-value	p-value
Indirect Effect Components	LLS → DS → EP	0.358	0.044	8.096	0.000
Direct Effect	LLS → EP	0.393	0.049	7.997	0.000
Total Effect	LLS → EP	0.751	0.050	14.967	0.000

Ratio Index = 0.4767

Legend:

LLS – Language Learning Strategies

DS – Debugging Strategies

EP – English Proficiency

Additionally, the table indicates the results of the computation of the effect size in the mediation test conducted between the three variables. The effect size measures how much of the effect of language learning strategies on the English proficiency of the students can be attributed to the indirect path. As shown in the figure, the ratio index obtains a value of 0.4767, indicating that about 47.67 percent of the total effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable goes through the mediator variable, and about 52.33 percent of the total effect is either direct or mediated by other variables not included in the model. The significant role of debugging strategies as a mediator in the relationship between language learning strategies and the students' English proficiency is contributed by the fact that there exists a relationship among these variables. It is emphasized in this study that debugging strategies are an

undeniable factor that has a positive relationship between language learning strategies and English proficiency of the students in Cluster 5 Schools in Davao City. Through mediation analysis, the mediation model shown in Figure 2 was generated. This is in accordance with the study of Gilakjani and Ahmadi (2011), which found that analyzing one's own particular learning strategy can be very helpful and beneficial to the student's motivation to be competitive academically by aiding them in becoming attentive learners, which ultimately will increase educational success. Finally, the results of the study support the theory anchored in this study, which is the Nativist Theory of Language Learning. The theory posits that individuals are born with a specific language-learning area in their brains. The theory suggests that students learn a language much like they learn how to count through repetition and reinforcement. Thus, uti-

Fig. 2. Mediation Model

lizing an effective learning strategy hereby provides the students with skills for them to be highly proficient in the English language.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This part of the paper presents the conclusions and recommendations of the researcher. The discussions were supported by the literature presented in the first chapters, and the conclusions were in accordance with statements of the problem presented in this study.

4.1. Summary of the Findings—The study primarily aimed to determine the role of debugging strategies as a mediator on language learning strategy and English proficiency of the students utilizing non-experimental quantitative design using structural equation modeling through mediation analysis. The researcher selected the 200 junior high school students in Cluster 5 Schools in Davao City Division as the respondents through a stratified random sampling method. The researcher made use of modified and enhanced adapted survey questionnaires, which were pilot-tested in a nearby school to ensure high reliability and internal consistency of the items in the instrument. On the one hand, the result showed that the extent of the language learning strategy of the students has an overall mean of 3.45 with a descriptive rating of extensive. Language learning strategy in terms of memory strategy, cognitive strategies, compen-

sation strategies, metacognitive strategy, affective strategy, and social strategy obtained mean scores of 3.36, 3.46, 3.41, 3.59, 3.32, and 3.55, respectively. On the other hand, the findings of the study indicate that the extent of English proficiency of the students in Cluster 5 Schools in Davao City has an overall mean of 3.43 with a descriptive rating of extensive. English proficiency in terms of spoken tasks, comprehension, interaction strategies, qualities of spoken performance, and writing tasks obtained mean scores of 3.28, 3.43, 3.36, 3.26, and 3.80, respectively. Adding more, descriptive analysis showed that the extent of debugging strategies of the students in Cluster 5 Schools in Davao City has an overall mean of 3.69 with a descriptive rating of extensive. Moreover, Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis showed that language learning strategies have a significant positive relationship with the English proficiency

of the students in Cluster 5 Schools in Davao City with a p-value of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .523$, $p < 0.05$). On the one hand, the language learning strategy has a significant positive relationship with the debugging strategies with a p-value of .000, which was less than the .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .749$, $p < 0.05$). On the other hand, debugging strategies have a significant positive relationship with the English proficiency of the students in Cluster 5 Schools in Davao City with a p-value of .000 that was less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .842$, $p < 0.05$). In addition, structural equation modeling through mediation analysis indicated that debugging strategies mediate the relationship between language learning strategies and English proficiency of the students in Cluster 5 Schools in Davao City. The analysis obtained the estimates value of 0.358 with $p < 0.05$, 0.393 with $p < 0.05$, and 0.751 with $p < 0.05$ for indirect, direct, and total effects, respectively. Moreover, the ratio index obtained a value of 0.4767, indicating that about 47.67 percent of the total effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable goes through the mediator variable, and about 52.33 percent of the total effect was either direct or mediated by other variables not included in the model.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the findings of this study, several conclusions were generated: First, the extent of the language learning strategy of the students in Cluster 5 schools in Davao City was extensive. Also, the extent of language learning strategies of the students in terms of cognitive strategies, compensation strategies, metacognitive strategy, and social strategy obtained an extensive descriptive rating, while language learning strategies in terms of memory strategy and affective strategy got a moderately extensive rating. The result denotes that students oftentimes used the learning strategies that enhanced their' motivation, which helped them adopt more positive atti-

tudes toward learning. Second, the extent of English proficiency of the students in Cluster 5 Schools in Davao City is extensive. The extent of English proficiency of the students in terms of comprehension and writing tasks was descriptively rated as extensive, while English proficiency in terms of spoken tasks, interaction strategies, and qualities of spoken performances acquired a moderately extensive rating. The result suggests that the ability of students to use the English language to make and communicate meaning in spoken and written contexts while completing their program of study is oftentimes evident among the respondents. Third, the extent of the students' debugging strategies in Cluster 5 Schools in Davao City was extensive. This implies that the strategies used to correct comprehension and performance errors were oftentimes evident. Fourth, the language learning strategies were found to have a significant positive relationship with Cluster 5 Schools in Davao City. Also, debugging strategies have a significant positive relationship with the English proficiency of the students in Cluster 5 Schools in Davao City. Lastly, it was found that debugging strategies mediate the relationship between language learning strategies and the student's English proficiency in Cluster 5 Schools in Davao City. This suggests that debugging strategies were an undeniable factor that has a positive relationship between language learning strategies and the English proficiency of the students in Cluster 5 Schools in Davao City.

4.3. Recommendations—Based on the conclusions generated in this study, the researcher recommends the following: School administrators may be recommended to empower their teachers to be acquainted with the knowledge and skills for teaching learning strategies, highlighting effective strategies through training, seminars, workshops, and the like, and later incorporating said strategies into teaching vocabulary. The extensive rating on stu-

dents' English proficiency indicates that these variables may still be improved to a higher status by employing programs and activities that could effectively increase students' English language proficiency. These activities may be done during Independent Classroom Learning (ICL) time. The result also shows that spoken tasks obtained the lowest scores among other indicators of English language proficiency. To address this, teachers should foster an atmosphere of motivation within the classroom. Allowing students to set and track their learning goals may instill a sense of ownership. Additionally, providing students with choice and control over what they study may enhance their curiosity as well as increase their proficiency in the English language. Moreover, since it was found that increasing the extent of learning strategy led to an increase in English language proficiency, the researcher recommends that school policymakers consider language learning strategy factors in implementing educational programs. Lastly, researchers should conduct further analysis on the factors that may contribute to the relationship between language learning strategies and English proficiency of the students in Cluster 5 Schools in Davao City since only 47.67 percent of the total effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable goes through the mediator variable.

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